

Studies on Hydrazones, Semicarbazones, Thiosemicarbazones and Oximes as Ligands. Part II—Some Divalent Metal Complexes of Benzil Monoxime

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A number of complexes of the composition MLX_2 or ML_2X_2 , where M is Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn, Cd; X is Cl^- , NCS^- , NO_2^- or ClO_4^- and L is benzil monoxime have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data.

As a part of our researches¹⁻⁷ on complexes of Schiff bases and related species we describe here some complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn and Cd salts with benzil monoxime as the ligand.

Experimental

Benzil monoxime was prepared according to a reported method⁸. Ethanolic solution of different divalent metal salts were reacted with the ligand in 1:2 proportion and the resulting solution was refluxed from 30 min to 1 hr. Solutions were concentrated in a rotary vacuum evaporator and kept overnight in a refrigerator when crystalline compounds separated out. Addition of petroleum ether was necessary in some cases for the isolation of the compounds. These were filtered under suction, washed with small quantity of absolute ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum. Metal, halogen, thiocyanate and nitrogen were estimated as reported earlier^{6,7}. Conductance was measured in $M/1000$ acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-621 spectrophotometer. Visible electronic spectra were recorded in $M/100$ chloroform solution of the compounds using Hillger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and some of the spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are crystalline. Manganese complexes are light yellow, cobalt complexes brown or orange excepting the chloride complex which is blue. Nickel(II) chloride complex is green, others

are yellow, copper complexes blue or green and zinc and cadmium complexes are white or light yellowish white in colour. All the compounds have low molar conductance values in acetone medium indicating non electrolytic nature excepting the nickel perchlorate complex which is 1:2 electrolyte. Magnetic moments of manganese complexes are in the range of 5.8-5.9 B.M. Cobalt chloride complex has the μ_{eff} value of 4.4 B.M. indicating a tetrahedral environment, whereas other compounds have higher moments (Table 1) suggestive of an octahedral configuration.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF BENZIL MONOXIME(L) COMPLEXES

Compounds	ΔM mhos.cm ² (B.M.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%metal		%Halogen, thiocyanate or nitrogen	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. MnLCl ₂	10.5	5.8	15.34	15.65	20.05	20.23
2. MnL(NO ₂) ₂	10.8	5.9	13.24	13.60	10.11	10.40
3. MnL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	238	5.9	7.36	7.80	3.72	3.98
4. CoLCl ₂	11.4	4.5	16.46	16.60	19.84	20.0
5. CoL ₂ (NCS) ₂	12.8	4.9	9.31	9.42	18.25	18.56
6. CoL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	12.5	4.9	9.11	9.31	8.42	8.85
7. CoL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	10.8	5.1	7.48	7.76	3.81	3.96
8. NiL ₂ Cl ₂	8.5	3.1	9.85	10.13	12.01	12.25
9. NiL(NCS) ₂	10.2	Diamag.	14.88	14.69	29.15	29.02
10. NiL(NO ₂) ₂	8.8	"	14.42	14.39	10.12	10.30
11. [NiL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	245	"	8.35	8.30	3.82	3.96
12. CuL ₂ Cl ₂	12.1	1.78	10.68	10.87	12.24	12.15
13. CuL ₂ (NCS) ₂	8.0	1.81	10.21	10.09	18.11	18.43
14. CuL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	10.4	1.82	9.55	9.97	8.45	8.78
15. [CuL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	241	1.79	8.58	8.92	3.69	3.93
16. ZnLCl ₂	12.6	—	18.15	18.09	19.42	19.65
17. ZnL(NO ₂) ₂	11.9	—	15.58	15.78	10.02	10.13
18. ZnL(NCS) ₂	12.0	—	16.22	16.08	28.32	28.54
19. CdLCl ₂	8.4	—	27.42	27.52	17.15	17.38
20. CdL(NCS) ₂	6.8	—	24.28	24.79	25.29	25.58

TABLE 2 SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME COMPLEXES INFRARED SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA

Compound No.	$\nu_{(OH)}$	$\nu_{(C=O)}$	$\nu_{(C=N)}$	$\nu_{(M=O)}$	$\nu_{(M=N)}$	ν_{max} in k.k(e)
1.	3710	1630	1590	460	320	20.0(1), 22.4(1.5), 23.2(2)
3.	3250	1630	1590	460	325	20.2(1), 22.3(2), 23.5(2)
4.	3200	1635	1580	465	320	16.4(890)
5.	3300	1640	1585	460	330	19.2(38), 20.0
7.	3250	1630	1580	465	330	19.4(40), 20.2
8.	3210	1635	1585	475	335	9.8(6), 14.5(13), 24.8(16)
11.	3250	1640	1590	470	330	14.8(60)
12.	3210	1640	1585	480	325	14.5(35)
15.	3300	1630	1580	475	330	15.0(33)
16.	3210	1630	1590	480	325	—

All the nickel complexes are diamagnetic except the chloride complex which has the μ_{eff} value of 3.1 B.M. Copper complexes have the moments in the range of 1.78-1.82 B.M.

In the infrared region, benzil monoxime has main absorption bands at 3350, 1660 and 950 cm⁻¹ regions assignable^{9,10} to $\nu_{(O-H)}$, $\nu_{(C=O)}$, $\nu_{(C=N)}$ and $\nu_{(N-O)}$ respectively. In the complexes $\nu_{(O-H)}$ is found ~ 3300 cm⁻¹ region and in the chloro-complex ~ 3210 cm⁻¹ possibly due to hydrogen bonding with the halogen. $\nu_{(C=O)}$ is observed in the 1630-1640 cm⁻¹ region and $\nu_{(C=N)}$ around 1580-1590 cm⁻¹ region. This lowering of the carbonyl and C=N stretching indicates^{11,12} the bonding of the carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms to the metal ions. This has been confirmed by the observation¹³ of $\nu_{(M=O)}$ and $\nu_{(M=N)}$ around 460-480 and 320-335 cm⁻¹ region respectively. In the case of the thiocyanato complexes $\nu_{(C=N)}$ is observed $\sim 2090-2100$ cm⁻¹ indicative¹⁴ of the presence of N-bonded terminal thiocyanato group, whereas in the cadmium complex this band is observed at 2135 cm⁻¹ suggestive of terminal sulfur coordination. In the nitrate complexes ν_4 and ν_1 bands are observed around 1280 and 1410 cm⁻¹ and the difference $\Delta\nu$ of the order of 130 cm⁻¹ confirms^{15,16} monodentate nitrate group coordination. Nickel, copper and manganese perchlorate complexes have a broad hump ~ 1100 cm⁻¹ and the cobalt complex has three absorption bands at 1155, 1090 and 1000 cm⁻¹ indicative^{17,18} of ionic perchlorate group in the former and coordinated one in the later complexes respectively.

In the visible electronic spectra of manganese complexes three bands are observed around 20.0, 22.4 and 23.2 k.k. regions assignable¹⁹ to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_2(G)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$ transitions

respectively. On the basis of the band positions and extinction coefficient value a tetrahedral geometry is presumed for these compounds. Cobalt chloride complex has an intense band at 16.4 k.k. Its position, intensity and the magnetic moment value confirms the tetrahedral geometry of the complex. Other cobalt complexes have absorption band around 19.2 k.k. region with a shoulder on the high frequency side attributable²⁰ to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions indicating a possible octahedral configuration. Absorption bands below 8.0 k.k. region could not be recorded due to the limitation of the instrument. Nickel chloride complex gives rise to three absorption bands at 9.8, 14.5 and 24.8 k.k. regions due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively indicating a spin free octahedral configuration in conformity with its magnetic moment value, whereas other nickel complexes show one band around 14.5-15.6 k.k. regions. The spectral pattern and diamagnetic nature of the complexes indicate²¹ a square planar configuration. All the copper complexes exhibit one broad absorption band around 14.5-15.3 k.k. regions indicating a distorted octahedral configuration²². On the basis of analyses, conductance and infrared spectral data, the zinc and cadmium complexes presumably have a tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

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